

Benefits and challenges of content and language integrated learning

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Abstract

In the digitalized world, various approaches have adopted, implemented and utilized to disseminate information to the learners in the world. One of the more promising methods to teach both content and the target language is Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL). The present paper discusses about the benefits and challenges in the successful implementation of CLIL. The main focus of the paper is to explore the various advantages of using this approach in the ESL classroom and it also presents the problems such as teacher problems and student problems faced during its implementation. It is suggested that CLIL approach may lead to a greater linguistic proficiency and it also boosts the motivation of the learners. So, it is appropriate for the learners of all age groups and their abilities that lead to a greater intercultural awareness. At the end, the paper provides implications to the teachers, trainers who wish to practice this approach in their classroom.

Key words: CLIL, Content and Language Integrated Learning, Methodology, Content based instruction, CBI

Introduction

In the digitalized world, various approaches have adopted, implemented and utilized to disseminate information to the learners in the world. There are many methods of teaching English at the disposal. The language learning has recently changed radically which brought many new methods and approaches in the language teaching especially for teaching English. For the past few decades, content-based instruction (CBI), also popular as content and language integrated learning (CLIL) has materialized as a new paradigm in the second language education. The manifestation of CLIL in language education and its execution across educational settings has drastically transformed the role of language teachers and language curriculum in primary and secondary level contexts and in the post secondary settings.

The present paper attempts to define CLIL elaborately and provides different techniques and activities involved in the approach. Content and Language Integrated Learning is a methodological approach for teaching the academic subject matter through the target language i.e. English. According to Freeman (2000) content based instruction (CBI) is that it integrates the learning of language with the learning of some other content, often academic subject matter (p.137). Academic subjects generally provide natural content for language instruction/ learning. In this approach, the

learners gain knowledge and comprehend the content while learning and using the target language. According to Coyle et al. (2010) CLIL is a dual- focused educational approach in which an additional language is used for the learning and teaching of both content and language (p.1). In this approach, the content is given equal important as target language. Coyle (1999) opines that CLIL has 4 Cs Framework such as content, communication, cognition and culture/ community in order to assist learners' linguistic progress and acquisition of subject knowledge.

LANGUAGE

In this approach, the language is derived from the academic content/ subject. This is characterized by:

- Ø a prevalence of content- related vocabulary
- Ø language is used for explanation, discussion and writing about content
- Ø language is for developing cognitive skills i.e. defining, giving reasons and opinions, evaluation, conclusion
- Ø language for mounting learning skills i.e. finding, interpreting, analysis and categorizing information

Language is some extend simplified, but it is not structurally graded. In the CLIL setting, the language facilitates the students to browse the content. According Coyle (2010), the language in this approach meant for the language is of learning (an analysis of language needed for learners to access basic concept and skills relating to the subject), for learning (strategies needed for learners to enable the use of target language effectively) and through learning (when learners are motivated to articulate their understanding, then a deeper level of learning takes place) (p.35-37). Teachers may prefer to divide language and subject matter thus making the learning of English difficult. Hence the students find learning language is a boring and tedious task.

TYPES OF CLIL

According to Bentley (2010) there are three types of CLIL in the curriculum. They are

1. Soft CLIL: it is practiced as part of a language course.
2. Hard CLIL: it is practiced as a partial immersion program, almost half of the curriculum is taught in the target language.
3. Modular CLIL: in this type, a subject is taught for a certain number of hours in the target language. (p.6)

Davies (2003) opines that there are three different models of CLIL in usage such as a 'sheltered model' where a subject specialist and a language teacher work together, an 'adjunct model' where a language teachers prepare classes to get used to students in

classes with other proficient learners, and a ‘theme based model’ where a teacher teaches on his/her own to open and construct upon the students’ own interests.

BENEFITS OF CLIL

CLIL approach offers many advantages to learners or teachers in the language classroom.

- ü A natural way of learning a language and a real way of approaching a content/subject.
- ü It enhances students’ motivation to learn what is being taught in the classroom.
- ü It enables students to learn more quickly and easily to improve overall and specific language competence.
- ü The students will develop a stronger understanding of culture context as a result of CLIL instruction in order to differentiate language and society.
- ü Through this instruction students build confidence in their abilities and academic skills are encouraged.
- ü It is suitable for students who have different learning styles.
- ü By using wider range of task types in this approach may help students understand better.
- ü Students are involved in more cognitive effort.ü Students develop multilingual interests and attitudes.
- ü CLIL creates opportunities for natural language learning.
- ü Teachers have liberty to change teaching method and employ a diversity of instructional tools in the classroom.
- ü At the end, a good way of approaching the curriculum in the classroom.

HOW EFFECTIVE ARE CLIL TECHNIQUES?

If the topics are selected based on learners’ interests and needs, the content is taught at the optimum level to increase students’ language proficiency. In CLIL approach, the students play an active role in the classroom, in order to participate in the most of the activities; they need to interact with others through the target language where the content is presented in the class. The strategy of teaching content through language, the learners perceive it as more interesting and perform faster way of learning. However, the learners are developing knowledge and they are more active in the classes which motivate them to learn and involve themselves in the process of learning.

LEARNING TYPES AND ACTIVITIES

This approach generally concentrates more on increasing in an interactive awareness on content knowledge, skills and cognitive skills through content learning. This interactive methodology enables in exploring the content and also acquiring the language. The activities involved in this approach is from group to pair activities, class quiz, the lead activity, conversations in pairs, poster presentation and oral presentation. The class offers plenty of choices to the students for learning skills and knowledge other than linguistic – team work, cooperation, negotiation, meeting a deadline, project work, and peer revision so on so forth. Teacher would adopt variety of activities for language use such as content questions, motivating activities, teaching vocabularies, post reading activities focusing on students' critical thinking, cooperative learning activities and speaking activities.

TEACHER'S PROBLEM/TEACHER ROLE

The classes can be taught either a subject teacher or a language teacher. Subject teachers should have command over the content as well as target language in order to be successful in their teaching through this approach. In CLIL, the teacher should be creative towards his/her approach to teaching academic subject and language. Though, CLIL is an interactive teaching style, the teachers must adopt a variety of effective teaching strategies such as project-based learning and problem based learning in the classroom. Besides, it may require the collaboration and cooperation between content teacher and language teacher, so that this approach may be effectively taught by helping each other in their content and language. It is challenging to guide, design and structure a well content based language instruction in the class. The teacher does not have liberty to use language freely because she/he needs to focus on learners' needs and necessities in their professional context/life. Time Management in the classroom is one of the major problems to be faced by the teachers during the CLIL instruction. The activities which to be conducted in the class may take longer than they are expected, because the students may take more time for involving with other students. The learners would have taken more time and find them difficulty to participate, if the activities had not carefully planned.

This approach is demanding for teachers in terms of adjusting practice and developing competences and that require prior training. Subject/Content teachers need to be able to present explain concepts clearly and accurately. They must check their pronunciation of subject-specific terms and their meaning and usage in different contexts. And also they must be able to use appropriate classroom language to present new topics/ concepts in English.

Language teachers are required to teach subject/ content in CLIL approach. They must be confident enough to teach knowledge and skills related to the subject they are

going to teach. One of the challenges faced by the language teacher is lack of expertise both in content areas and in the discipline- specific pedagogy within which language teaching is fixed. They must develop their knowledge of content vocabulary and its pronunciation. The most of important challenges is to find appropriate material for content classes. In CLIL approach, the assessment generally complicated for the teachers whether to assess content, language or both. Most of the teachers are not familiar with the implementation of CLIL.

STUDENTS' PROBLEMS

As it is well known that whenever, the teacher asks questions to the students, and then they unable to express their responses in the target language. So, most of the learners through this approach overcome the inhibition of their lack of self- confidence and naturally exhibit language performance. Through this approach, the students learn language unconsciously through the academic subject. When the students are involved in the content their focus is on subject matter so they give least priority to the target language. The focus of the class is on comprehending the content so students communicate in the target language making mistakes without any inhibition. The students may feel bore and confusion in the class due to academic subject teaching continuously. But, in reality most of the students are accustomed to mother tongue to learn subject/ content most of the time. Even the subject teachers teach content through their mother tongue. The students also use their first language when they are unable to comprehend/ present in the target language.

DISADVANTAGES

Content and language integrated learning approach has a number of demerits along with its myriad advantages. The following are some of the disadvantages of CLIL:

- Ø This approach lacks of linguistic competence in English.
- Ø It does not motivate all the students in the class to learn a second language.
- Ø There is no clear preference to teach any specific subjects.
- Ø It is essential for special training for teachers focusing on CLIL approach.
- Ø CLIL is mostly implemented in secondary schools and the learners do not required to be proficient in English to follow the content (Graddol, 2006).
- Ø Language is learned lexically rather than grammatically.
- Ø The inadequate CLIL materials and resources can be a serious problem in preparation of lesson plans.
- Ø Choosing and adapting content and teaching materials are time consuming; hence it . becomes an obstacle in the material production.

- Ø Students may find that CLIL isn't explicitly focused on language learning.
- Ø Complexity in the content may lead to the use of mother tongue in the classroom.
- Ø Difficulties in finding materials for low level students to comprehend.
- Ø At the end, students may simply copy from available texts without any attempt.

IMPLICATIONS

For unsuccessful CLIL classroom instruction, there are insufficient trained and qualified teachers for teaching and for implementing this instruction. It is essential to provide appropriate training for the teachers especially new teachers to be competent in teaching through CLIL approach. In training the more focus should be on the integration of content with the language in order to obtain the language competence and proficiency. The concerned authorities should conduct special in house training for all the teachers to update their skills and to solve problems faced during their teaching in the monthly basis regularly. The development of CLIL curricula requires to be established and more research is also requisite in order to the emphasis of environmental aspects. However, CLIL learners would become more successful in learning both the content and target language and they obtain better results in the exams. The curriculum designers should produce materials in such a way that fill the gap between subject and language. In this approach, the teachers should assess students' knowledge of content and language.

CONCLUSION

In a language point of view the CLIL approach provides lots of opportunities to the teacher to implement in the classroom. The teachers should pay more attention to few things while conducting the classroom activities. The activities should be interesting and it must include additional information. In that the learners must involve very enthusiastically. It develops learners' self confidence and motivation which provides a pleasant atmosphere to the classroom. However, the subject teachers may find it unethical, not up to the mark to use this approach in the classroom to teach both content and target language.

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